

Genome Assemblage of *Pachymelania fusca* from two Connecting Tropical Lagoons in Lagos, Nigeria

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1. Introduction

Molluscs are the largest invertebrate animals and are important resources that contribute considerable economic value to the world's fisheries (MolluscaBase, 2023, Okunade *et al.*, 2020). Phylum mollusca, is a diverse group of triploblastic protozoans, known for their soft bodies and un-segmented anatomy (Brusca, 2005). Additionally, it ranks third to arthropoda and nematoda in terms of numbers of species (estimated at 130,000, which does not include the 35,000 fossilized species) (Runnegar and Pojeta, 1974). Thus far phylum Mollusca has about 100,000 described species and potentially 100,000 species yet to be taxonomically identified (Strong *et al.*, 2008). It is divided among seven classes (Ruppert *et al.*, 2004) and is present on nearly every continent.

One group of Mollusca, gastropods are one of the broadest distributed eukaryotic taxa, being present across ecosystems worldwide. They occupy a maximally diverse set of habitats ranging from the deep sea to the highest mountains and from deserts to the Arctic, and have evolved to a range of specific adaptations (Romero *et al.* 2015, 2016). However, in general, their species richness is second only to the arthropods (Dunn and Ryan 2015), With Gastropoda is the largest (40000 species) and most diverse, containing spirally coiled snails, flat-shelled limpets, shell-less sea slugs and terrestrial snails and slugs.

The genus *Pachymelania* adapts to fresh water but prefers brackish water of higher salinity and is often extremely abundant in the mangrove swamps and on the mud flats within reach of the tide, in the lagoons and estuaries (Okunade *et al.*, 2020). The gastropod, *Pachymelania fusca* (Gmelin, 1791) is a representative of family Melanidae, Super family Cerithiacea and they are found in lagoons, estuaries and mangrove swamps of West Africa (Okunade *et al.*, 2020).

Sigwart *et al.* (2021) reported that mollusc genomes in particular have become available only very recently: Of the 53 partial or complete genomes of mollusc publicly available half (25 genomes) have been published since 2019 (Sigwart *et al.* 2021). This growing availability of genome information holds significant potential for advancing effective breeding techniques and

promoting mollusc aquaculture (Takeuchi, 2017). The draft genomes of the pearl oyster, *Pinctada fucata*, and the Pacific oyster, *Crassostrea gigas*, were the first molluscan genomes published (Takeuchi *et al* 2012; Zhang *et al.* 2012). Since then, genomes of 13 mollusc species in 3 classes (Bivalvia, Gastropoda, and Cephalopoda) have been published (Murgarella *et al* 2016). In addition, some molluscan genome assemblies, such as that of *Aplysia californica*, are publicly available.

In this work, we present the genome assemblage of *Pachymelania fusca* (Plate. 1). This would be an important foundation for future genomic and applied research in this scientifically important Mollusc.

2. METHODS

Macrobenthic invertebrates were collected from Ologe (longitude 6°27 and 6°30 N and latitude 3°2 and 3°7E) and Badagry Lagoons (longitude 3° 45 and latitude 6° 30 N) in southwestern, Nigeria between August 2016 and July 2018. Species of *Pachymelania fusca* (Gmelin, 1791) from each lagoon, which were selected for a genomics study due to their availability in both lagoons and all through the two years of collection. Genomic DNA was extracted from the muscle of *Pachymelania fusca* from each lagoon, which were selected for a genomic study due to their availability in both lagoons and all through the two years of collection. Raw reads have been deposited under NCBI BioProject PRJNA681324

Plate 1: *Pachymelania fusca*

2.1 Reads Processing and Genome Assembly

The two reads were separately assembled at the different assembly processes. Each read was first submitted to a use galaxy genome assemble pipeline (Galaxy Community, 2022) with a single-end layout on illumina platform, SPAdes v3.12.0 assembler (Bankevich, *et al* 2012) was used during the assembling process, reads were trimmed with Trim Galore 0.6.5de (Krueger and Galor 2015) followed by two polishing rounds of Pilon 1.23 used to improves draft genome assemblies by correcting bases, fixing miss-assemblies and filling gaps (Walker *et al* 2014). Then Contigs were filtered based on length and coverage and produced in FASTA format. UGENE software was used to generate a consensus sequence for each read (Okonechnikov, 2012).

2.2 Functional Genome Annotation

The first annotation process was performed using the AUGUSTUS genome annotation tool (Stanke *et al* 2006) which employs gene prediction algorithms based on the genetic code suitable for the species. Galaxy pipeline database was utilized for this process, taking advantage of its robust and flexible data processing capabilities. This ensured that our large and complex genomic dataset was handled efficiently and accurately. AUGUSTUS was run with *Caenorhabditis elegans* model organism (Hoff *et al* 2013) as a predefined trained dataset. This trained dataset was used in other to allow the tool to adapt to the specific characteristics and genetic code of the snail genome. The second annotation process was performed using GENEIOUS software v9.0.5 annotation tools for homology-based gene predictions (Kearse *et al* 2012). This was conducted by aligning annotated gene features from the NCBI database (Coordinators 2018) with Gastropod species as reference genomes to the masked genome with the Plasmapper tool (Grant and Stothard 2008) in Geneious v9.0.5 which helped precisely to identify similar genes in the snail genome. . Annotation of repeat elements in the genome was performed using the Repeat-finder v1.0 tool in Geneious v9.0.5 (www.geneious.com). This tool allowed us to identify and annotate repetitive sequences, A comprehensive repeat sequence library was compiled. This library is essential for understanding the genomic structure and evolutionary aspects of the snail.

2.3 Mapping to References and Gene Expression Profile Analysis

The assembly genome for both *P. fusca* samples from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons were mapped to *Pomacea canaliculata* genome as a reference using Geneious Software v9.0.5. (Conesa *et al* 2016) By comparing expression levels of genes at 81.8°C to the reference genome in each read, 2247 genes were MAPPED for differential gene expression (DEGs) from *Pachymelania fusca* from both Lagoons respectively.

2.4 Determination of Stress Genes Expression Profile

After the calculation of gene expression levels of each read and the expression rate was compared against a reference annotated sequence for each track, TPM values of each gene from all conditions were calculated using Geneious differential gene expression tool based on the median expression of each gene and at rough Tm: 81.8°C. An expressed gene was defined using a cut off of ≥ 1 TPM in both biological replicates. Then expression levels (RPKM and TPM) were calculated for each reads annotation. The expression data from two annotated reads were used to determine the Reads Per Kilobase of transcript, per Million mapped reads (RPKM) values and then use the values to get differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in the spleen between the two annotated sample reads on the reference genome.

2.5 Phylogenetic Tree Construction of *P. fusca*

To construct the phylogenetic tree, *Achatina fulica* reference genes were downloaded from NCBI database. The comparative analysis was obtained using the Muscle alignment tool (Saitou and Nei 1987) with the following parameters: Global alignment with free end gaps, Cost matrix identity of (1.0/0.0), Gap open penalty of 12 and extension of 3, and Refinement iterations of 2. The phylogenetic tree was constructed using Neighbor-Joining and the maximum likelihood based on the genetic distance model (Price, 2010) with a bootstrap value of 1000 and 100 numbers of replicates. This was edited with Geneious tree builder version 9.0.5 to determine the evolutionary relatedness and diversities. Comparative analysis of genes with a distance matrix of the tree was performed on Geneious (<https://www.geneious.com/>) based on statistical analysis to determine positions of significant difference between the genes.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Genomic Characterization of *P. fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons

Genome Assembly

The report on the assembly for *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons shows significant characteristics across different genomic parameters as shown in table 1. Precisely, the genome length of Ologe Lagoon sample is 107,923 bp which comprises 1,634 contigs, a GC content of 45.47%, a contig L50 of 706, and a contig N50 of 60. When compared to the genome length of Badagry Lagoon sample, it has 6,565 bp with only 74 contigs, a higher GC content of 53.27%, a contig L50 of 33, and a contig N50 of 97. Despite this significant difference, both samples consist of the same coarse and fine consistency of 93.9% indicating a robust assembly process without significant bias. Re-mapping the preprocessed reads using Geneious software v9.0.5 showed consistent read placement and uniform genome representation via coverage distribution for both samples. The cumulative length of all contigs for both samples with indicated differences in genome length and contig numbers was suggested to be a result of variations in environmental factors, sample quality, or inherent biological differences between the populations from the two lagoons. Overall, this analysis shows a more complex and high diversity in sequence assembly which may reflect on the ecological or biological differences between the two locations (Lischer and Shimizu 2010). This study established the characterization of the genome of *P. fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons. The genome information could contribute to the development of effective breeding and sustainable mollusc aquaculture (Takeuchi, 2017). The draft genomes of the pearl oyster, *Pinctada fucata*, and the Pacific oyster, *Crassostrea gigas*, were the first molluscan genomes published (Takeuchi *et al* 2012; Zhang *et al.* 2012). Since then, genomes of thirteen mollusc species in three classes (Bivalvia, Gastropoda, and Cephalopoda) have been published (Murgarella *et al* 2016). In addition, some molluscan genome assemblies, such as that of *Aplysia californica*, are publicly available. Varied genome sizes among molluscs reflect, in part, the number of repetitive sequences. In the *P. fusca* genome, the estimated genome size was 169MB. This assembled genome had 1,634 contigs, with the total length of 107,923 bp and an average G+C content of 45.47%.

Table 1: Assembly details for *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons

Statistics	Ologe Lagoon <i>Pachymelania fusca</i>	Badagry Lagoon <i>Pachymelania fusca</i>
Genome Length	107,923 bp	6,565 bp
Contigs	1,634	74
GC Content	45.47	53.27
Contig L50	706	33
Contig N50	60	97
Coarse consistency (%)	93.9	93.9
Fine consistency (%)	93.9	93.9

Figure 1: Genome Assembly Report for (A) *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe Lagoon

Figure 2: Genome Assembly Report *Pachymelania fusca* of Badagry Lagoon

The raw sequencing data generated during this study have been deposited at NCBI as a BioProject under accession PRJNA681324. Genomic and transcriptome sequence reads have been deposited in the SRA database with BioSample SAMN16949074. In the present study, the taxonomic sampling was based on the closest sequences of species *Achatina fulica* (Giant African land snail) obtained in Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) analysis in GenBank (Zhang et al 2012). The taxonomy of this genome is cellular organisms > Eukaryota > Opisthokonta > Metazoa > Eumetazoa > Bilateria > Protostomia > Spiralia > Lophotrochozoa > Mollusca > Gastropoda > unclassified Gastropoda > Gastropoda sp. IOP_0426 for both reads.

Table 2: Assembly data reports

Category	Ologe Lagoon	Badagry Lagoon	
	<i>Pachymelania fusca</i>	<i>Pachymelania fusca</i>	
Reference seq length:	45,418,633	45,418,633	
Sequences:	1,632	62	
Identical Sites:	11,866	455	
Coverage of bases	45,418,633	45,418,633	
Mean: 0.6	Std Dev: 1.7	Mean: 0.6	Std Dev: 1.1
Minimum: 0	Maximum: 46	Minimum: 0	Maximum: 6
Forward: 0.3	Reverse: 0.2	Forward: 0.2	Reverse: 0.4
Ref-Seq:	29.7% (13,501,054 of Ref-Seq: 27.3% 45,418,568)		27.3% (12,418,830 of 45,418,568)

Genome Annotation

Genome annotation of *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons revealed notable differences between the two samples as shown in Table 3. Annotation in Ologe Lagoon sample had a total of 2,689 genes, which is significantly higher than the 103 genes identified in Badagry Lagoon sample. This difference identified in Ologe Lagoon shows the genomic content to be more diverse and complex. The number of mRNA sequences further supports this complexity,

with Ologe Lagoon sample exhibiting 3,172.75 mRNA sequences compared to 193 in Badagry Lagoon sample.

Repeat sequences which play significant roles in genome stability and evolution (Treangen and , Salzberg 2012) , were also more prevalent in Ologe Lagoon (7,375 repeats) than in Badagry Lagoon (290 repeats). Likewise, open reading frames (ORFs) were more abundant in Ologe Lagoon sample as well, with 930 ORFs identified compared to 73 in Badagry Lagoon sample. The coding DNA sequences (CDS) were also prevalent in Ologe Lagoon, with 151 CDS, whereas Badagry Lagoon had only 30 CDS the predicted proteins were also substantially more prevalent in Ologe Lagoon sample (35,974 predicted proteins) compared to Badagry Lagoon sample (2,188)

In the protein-coding feature coverage, a significant insight was revealed between the two samples which includes Ologe Lagoon sample possesses a coverage of 139.91%, while Badagry Lagoon sample has a coverage of 456.97%. The high coverage noticed in Badagry Lagoon sample might as a result of a more concentrated set of protein-coding features relative to the smaller genome size observed. A similar percentage of hypothetical features was observed between both samples despite the differences in gene and feature counts with 100% of the features being hypothetical. This high percentage represents the necessity for further functional validation and characterization toward understanding the complete biological roles and significance of these features (Galperin, 2001).

Overall, the significant differences in the number of genes, mRNA sequences, repeats, ORFs, CDS, and predicted proteins between the two lagoons also indicate a higher level of genomic complexity in Ologe Lagoon which is the same case with genome assembly result. This complexity could be associated with various environmental factors, ecological interactions, or evolutionary changes specific to each lagoon (Tautz and Domazet-Lošo 2011). These findings highlight the importance of further research to explore the functional implications of these differences and to better understand the ecological and evolutionary dynamics of *Pachymelania fusca* in these distinct environments (Lynch and Conery,2000)

Table 3: Functional annotation details for *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons

Category	Ologe Lagoon	Badagry Lagoon
	<i>Pachymelania fusca</i>	<i>Pachymelania fusca</i>
Gene	2, 689	103
mRNA	3,172.75	193
Repeats	7,375	290
ORF	930	73
CDS	151	30
Predicted proteins	35, 974	2,188
% Protein-coding Feature Coverage	139.91	456.97
% Features that are Hypothetical	100	100

Mapping to Reference

Mapping the two genome data samples of *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoon respectively to *Pomacea canaliculate* as reference data lasted for 12 minutes and 59 seconds (15 minutes and 19 seconds CPU time). For sample data from Ologe lagoon, the process was performed under two iterations with the first matching 719 reads and the second 826 reads. At the end of the process, the results indicated that 1,631 out of 2,689 reads were mapped to the reference resulting in the formation of a contig, while 1,058 reads were not assembled. Similarly, for the Badagry Lagoon sample, the mapping duration lasted for 12 minutes and 15 seconds (13 minutes and 56 seconds CPU time). The process also involved two iterations, the first matching 49 reads while the second 61 reads. 61 out of 103 reads were mapped to the reference, resulting in the formation of a contig, while 42 reads were not assembled.

Differential Gene Expression Analysis

To evaluate the expression profile of genes in both *Pachymelania fusca* genomes, the relative expression levels (RPKM) of each transcript were estimated (figure 4). This analysis is significant for understanding the transcripts and genetic evolution influenced by the distinct environmental conditions in these habitats (Conesa *et al* 2016). In total, 855.0 expressed reads were detected in the Ologe Lagoon population and when

compared to the Badagry Lagoon only 28.0 reads were detected and this suggests a notably higher transcriptional activity in Ologe Lagoon sample. With the excluding of the upper quartile, Ologe Lagoon had 225.6 expressed reads and Badagry Lagoon had only 4.6. Also higher in the Ologe Lagoon samples is the median expressed reads of 0.4750 and 0.0098 in Badagry Lagoon. For the expressed transcripts in Ologe Lagoon, the total number was 4.0, and while Badagry Lagoon only 0.3 was expressed. With the upper quartile excluded, 0.7 expressed transcripts were noticed in Ologe Lagoon compared to Badagry Lagoon nothing was found. Also, the median expressed transcripts were higher in Ologe Lagoon (0.0015) than in Badagry Lagoon (0.0001). A minimum RPKM of 0.0 was detected in both lagoons indicating the presence of transcripts with no detectable expression, but the maximum RPKM was indeed detected in both Badagry Lagoon (46,102.8) and Ologe Lagoon (10,536.9). These results show that the maximum transcripts were significantly higher in Badagry Lagoon compared to Ologe Lagoon indicating very high expression levels for certain transcripts in Badagry Lagoon. The mean RPKM was higher in Badagry Lagoon (207.4) than in Ologe Lagoon (110.3), suggesting that although fewer transcripts were expressed in Badagry Lagoon, those that were expressed had higher levels. For the TPM values, it was shown that both lagoons had a mean TPM of 445.0. While the maximum TPM was much higher in Badagry Lagoon (98,943.1), in Ologe Lagoon, it was much lower at 42,523.5. This result further reinforces the observation of higher expression levels for specific transcripts in Badagry Lagoon. Ambiguously mapped reads were counted as partial matches in both datasets, ensuring consistent evaluation.

Determination of Stress Genes Expression Profile

In each read, the entire expression level of the genes at 81.8°C to the reference genome was compared for both samples. In *Pachymelania fusca* genomes from both lagoons, 2,247 genes were mapped for differential gene expression (DEGs) including 855 up-regulated and 1,362 down-regulated genes in from Ologe Lagoon, and 28 up-regulated and 2,222 down-regulated genes in from Badagry Lagoon. Furthermore, to determine whether any of the genotypes had similar profiles, the intersections of the up- and down-regulated DEGs were analyzed and the result showed that 1,362 genes from Ologe Lagoon were subject to stress, hence down-regulated, mostly due to environmental

factors (Zhao *et al* 2020) In comparison, 2,222 down-regulated genes were identified in the sample from Badagry Lagoon. The differences identified in the gene expression profiles highlight the important factors associated with the state of the environment especially those related to the genetic responses of *Pachymelania fusca* and understanding these responses is essential for conservative efforts such as predicting how these populations may adapt to different changes, or by identifying the key stressors associated to the environment which in turns affects these populations (Evans *et al* 2018). Understanding the functional roles of the differentially expressed genes is significant in providing deeper insights into the ecological and evolutionary dynamics of *Pachymelania fusca* found in these distinct lagoon environments (Love *et al* 2014)

Table 4: Differential expressed genes (DEGs) of *Pachymelania fusca* of Ologe and Badagry Lagoons.

Category	Ologe Lagoon <i>Pachymelania fusca</i>	Badagry Lagoon <i>Pachymelania fusca</i>
Reads - Total Expressed:	855.0	28.0
Total Expressed Excluding Upper Quartile:	225.6	4.6
Reads - Median Expressed:	0.4750	0.0098
Transcripts - Total Expressed:	4.0	0.3
Transcripts - Total Expressed Excluding Upper Quartile:	0.7	0.0
Transcripts - Median Expressed:	0.0015	0.0001
RPKM Minimum:	0.0	0.0
RPKM Mean:	110.3	207.4
RPKM Maximum:	10536.9	46102.8
TPM Minimum: 0.0	0.0	0.0
TPM Mean:	445.0	445.0
TPM Maximum: 42523.5	42523.5	98943.1
Ambiguously Mapped Reads:	Count as partial matches	Count as partial matches

Table 5: The relative expression levels (RPKM) of *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons

Category	Ologe Lagoon <i>Pachymelania fusca</i>	Badagry Lagoon <i>Pachymelania fusca</i>
Total Annotations Reads Expressed:	855.0	28.0
Total Annotations Transcripts Expressed:	4.0	4.0
Annotations-Transcripts-Median Expressed:	0.0015	0.0001
Value Compared:	Transcripts	Transcripts
Normalized By:	Median of Gene Expression Ratios	Median of Gene Expression Ratios

Figure 2: Gene Expression Annotations

Figure 3: Coverage covered per Expression level

Phylogenetic Analysis of *Pachymelinia fusca*

Sequence alignment of 22 sequences revealed Identical Sites of 486 (0.4%) and Pairwise % Identity of 9.3 % between the reference genes to the query sequence. Phylogenetic analysis using geneious tree builder revealed 3 branches each relative to the ancestral root with an identity value of 93 and 57 bootstrap score (Figures 4 and 5). *P. fusca* of Ologe and Badagry Lagoons were shown to be closely related in the same order as the subject genes. This signifies that the organism genes contained some conserved regions and homologous characters similar to the common ancestor as evolution took place over time in both assembly genomes (Kato *et al* 2002). Going down the tree to the last branch, the genes are genetically diverged and unrelated to the genes in the query genomes, and more diversifications surfaced. The sequenced and referenced organisms contained some conserved regions and homologous characters similar to the common ancestor as evolution took place over time in the genome. Going down the tree, more diversifications surfaced when compared to both query genome samples which signifies

that some of the subjected genome samples were genetically diverged and unrelated (Darling *et al* 2014).

Figure 4: Phylogenetic tree Analysis of *Pachymelania fusca* from Ologe and Badagry Lagoons

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Name	Description ▲	%GC	Topology	Molecule Type
<input type="checkbox"/>	SimRAD3_R1	-	45.5%	circular	-
<input type="checkbox"/>	SimRAD3_R2	-	53.3%	circular	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	WNKJ01000557_Achatina im...	Achatina immaculata isolate DP-2019 Undclustered_ctg3200_pilon, whole genome shotgun sequence	37.4%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	AASC03164542_Aplysia calif...	Aplysia californica isolate F4 #8 contig164542, whole genome shotgun sequence	37.8%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	KB944421_Aplysia californica	Aplysia californica isolate F4 #8 unplaced genomic scaffold scaffold03664, whole genome shotgun sequence	39.3%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	JACVVK010000863_Batillaria	Batillaria attramentaria isolate Wonlab-2016 001941F, whole genome shotgun sequence	51.2%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	JABXJC010002113_Biomphal...	Biomphalaria glabrata breed 1316-R1 isolate R68 Contig_R-002681, whole genome shotgun sequence	34.0%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	JABXJC010002023_Biomphal...	Biomphalaria glabrata breed 1316-R1 isolate R68 Contig_R-002685, whole genome shotgun sequence	37.1%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	NW_013524645_Biomphalari...	Biomphalaria glabrata isolate BB02 unplaced genomic scaffold, ASM45736v1 LGUN_random_Scaffold99999, whole genome shot...	35.4%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SMMR01000018_Chrysomall...	Chrysomallon squamiferum isolate Csq_Karei_E02B1 CsqKR_Scaf997, whole genome shotgun sequence	45.2%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	RQTK01009987_Elysia chlor...	Elysia chlorotica isolate EC2010 scaffold009987, whole genome shotgun sequence	37.1%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	RQTK01009988_Elysia chlor...	Elysia chlorotica isolate EC2010 scaffold009988, whole genome shotgun sequence	33.8%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	RQTK01009989_Elysia chlor...	Elysia chlorotica isolate EC2010 scaffold009989, whole genome shotgun sequence	34.6%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	NW_024537384_Gigantopelt...	Gigantopelta aegis isolate Gae_Host unplaced genomic scaffold, Gae_host_genome scaffold81, whole genome shotgun sequence	39.2%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SMGT01017147_Lanistes ny...	Lanistes nyassanus isolate A2010 Lan_Scaf_34143, whole genome shotgun sequence	45.0%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SMGT01017148_Lanistes ny...	Lanistes nyassanus isolate A2010 Lan_Scaf_34144, whole genome shotgun sequence	46.0%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SMGT01017149_Lanistes ny...	Lanistes nyassanus isolate A2010 Lan_Scaf_34145, whole genome shotgun sequence	48.3%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	NW_008708317_Lottia giga...	Lottia gigantea unplaced genomic scaffold LOTGIisca_18091, whole genome shotgun sequence	37.4%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	NW_008708324_Lottia giga...	Lottia gigantea unplaced genomic scaffold LOTGIisca_18115, whole genome shotgun sequence	35.5%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	FCFB01328377_Lymnaea st...	Lymnaea stagnalis genome assembly, contig: gLs.1.0.scaf148228_contig_1, whole genome shotgun sequence	45.8%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	FCFB01328378_Lymnaea st...	Lymnaea stagnalis genome assembly, contig: gLs.1.0.scaf148229_contig_1, whole genome shotgun sequence	52.6%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SRJH01002418_Pomacea ca...	Pomacea canaliculata isolate AR2004Pca_1000, whole genome shotgun sequence	40.7%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SRJH01002421_Pomacea ca...	Pomacea canaliculata isolate AR2004Pca_1001, whole genome shotgun sequence	39.8%	linear	DNA
<input type="checkbox"/>	SRHC01001716_Pomacea ca...	Pomacea maculata isolate AR2013Pma_1720, whole genome shotgun sequence	39.1%	linear	DNA

Figure 5: Showing data representation of all isolated sequences of the organisms

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